

PERCEPTIONS ON THE TEACHING OF READING SKILLS IN SENIOR HIGH: A COMPARATIVE STUDY AMONG STUDENTS AND TEACHERS IN METRO GENSAN

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ABSTRACT

This study compared the perceptions of both students and teachers regarding teachers' performance in teaching reading skills at the senior high level. Using a developed survey questionnaire from a preliminary study, the research surveyed a sample of 205 HUMSS 11 students and 14 English faculty teachers from three prominent schools in Metro Gensan, namely General Santos City National Secondary School of Arts and Trades (GSNSAT), Irineo L. Santiago National High School of Metro Dadiangas, and North National High School. Through a comprehensive analysis of survey data and statistical tests using weighted mean and Mann-Whitney U test, several key findings have emerged. Both subgroups revealed high perceptions of teachers' performance in teaching reading skills, with the teachers at 4.29 and the students at 3.87. While the majority of indicators reflect positive perceptions, areas for improvement have been identified, particularly concerning the identification and support of struggling students and the development of a stronger reading culture within schools. Notably, students and teachers share aligned perceptions regarding these areas, emphasizing the need for enhanced intervention programs and a supportive learning environment conducive to reading engagement. The rejection of the null hypothesis further underscores the necessity for educators to better understand students' perspectives and tailor instructional strategies accordingly. Moving forward, recommendations include investing in continuous professional development for teachers, strengthening intervention programs, fostering a reading-positive environment, facilitating open communication and collaboration among stakeholders, and employing data-driven decision-making processes.

Keywords: *Teaching Reading Skills, Senior High School, HUMSS 11, Student Perception, Teacher Perception, Reading Instruction.*

INTRODUCTION

Reading, considered a fundamental skill involving the decoding of symbols and comprehension of their meaning, is typically expected to be honed during a child's early education (Tadese, 2017). The Philippines, recognized globally as one of the largest English-speaking nations, has historically prided itself on the widespread fluency in English among its populace. However, recent years have witnessed a concerning decline in English proficiency, evident in various international and local assessments conducted on Filipino students from high school to college (Cabigon, 2015).

According to Education First (2019), the Philippines experienced a notable drop in its English proficiency index, falling from 14th to 20th place. Similarly, research by Hopkins International highlighted the inferior English proficiency levels of Philippine college graduates compared to high school students in Thailand and even taxi drivers in Dubai (Oducado, 2020). Moreover, recent data from the Programme for International Student Assessment ranked the Philippines last in reading comprehension among 79 countries (Mocon-Ciriaco, 2019). Despite assumptions that senior high or college students no longer require reading-focused curricula or programs, examination results and inquiries suggest otherwise.

In response to these challenges, the Department of Education has implemented various national and local reading initiatives, such as the Every Child a Reader Program and English for Academic and Professional Purposes (Agao, 2016; Diaz-Sabado, 2021). Nevertheless, while several studies have scrutinized reading programs and practices in the Philippines, few have delved deeply into how reading skills are taught and addressed at the senior high level. Moreover, there is a scarcity of research employing valid and reliable surveys to gather quantitative data on teaching reading skills in senior high schools.

Thus, this study aimed to investigate the current landscape of reading development in senior high schools, focusing on the teacher level of performance in teaching reading skills to senior high learners. The findings of this investigation could provide valuable insights into the importance of ongoing emphasis on reading development in senior high schools and the necessity for remedial reading interventions for senior high students.

Research Questions

This research aimed to compare the teachers' level of performance in teaching reading skills as perceived between the teachers and students of three prominent schools in Metro Gensan Area.

Specifically, this research aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the teachers' level of performance in teaching reading skills as perceived by the Teachers themselves?
2. What is the teachers' level of performance in teaching reading skills as perceived by the Students?
3. Is there a significant difference in the perception of teachers' performance level in teaching reading skills between the teachers and students?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design employed in this study is a causal-comparative survey design, as defined by Creswell and Creswell (2018). This design falls within the realm of nonexperimental quantitative research, which aims to compare two or more groups based on a predetermined cause or predictor variable that has already occurred. In this specific study, the researcher examined the ratings provided by both teachers and students regarding the teachers' performance in teaching reading skills. By comparing these perceptions, the study sought to determine whether differences in perception would lead to variations in the ratings of teaching performance.

Respondents

The participants in this study consisted of HUMSS Grade 11 students and senior high English faculty members from three prominent schools in the Metro Area of General Santos City, namely: General Santos City National Secondary School of Arts and Trades (GSNSAT), Irineo L. Santiago National High School of Metro Dadiangas, and North National High School. The researcher employed a systematic approach to identify the respondents, beginning with the calculation of the sample size. Using the Checkmarket sample size calculator with a 5% margin of error and 95% confidence level, the sample size was determined to be 205 from a population of 438 HUMSS 11 students across the three schools. Subsequently, the sample was stratified among the three schools, and convenience sampling was utilized to select the final student respondents. For the teacher respondents, total population sampling was employed, encompassing all 14 active teachers from the three schools. This rigorous sampling methodology ensured a representative and comprehensive selection of participants, thereby enhancing the validity and reliability of the study's findings.

Table 1*Respondents of the study*

	Students		Teachers	
	N	n	N	n
Irineo National High School	154	72	6	6
Lagao National High School	194	91	6	6
North National High School	90	42	2	2
<i>Total</i>	438	205	14	14

Instruments

The survey questionnaire used in this study was developed from a preliminary qualitative investigation. Originally comprising 40 items rated on a 5-point Likert scale, the questionnaire aimed to assess various aspects related to challenges encountered, strategies and approaches practiced, and interventions implemented in teaching reading skills at the senior high school level. However, for the purposes of this particular study, only Part Two and Three of the questionnaire were utilized, as they specifically targeted teachers' performance in teaching reading skills. Prior to implementation, the questionnaire underwent rigorous validation by four expert validators, including a psychologist, to ensure its content validity. Furthermore, its reliability was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient.

Table 2*Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Result*

Teacher Level of Performance in Teaching Reading Skills Survey	N of Items	CronBach's Alpha	Interpretation
Practice of Strategies and Approaches	20	.941	Highly Reliable
Implementation of intervention and Remediation			

Data Gathering Procedures

Upon the board's approval, the researcher composed a request letter addressed to the School Division Superintendent of General Santos City and the school heads of the three chosen schools, seeking permission to gather data within their institutions. Upon receiving approval, the researcher proceeded to collect data to calculate the required number of respondents. Following the development and validation of the research instrument, quantitative data were collected from the same schools. Informed consent forms were sent along with the survey questionnaire to ensure compliance with ethical procedures. Subsequently, the collected data were retrieved and analyzed using descriptive statistics.

Statistical Analysis

Weighted Mean. These descriptive statistics was used to analyze each respondent's score in the developed survey on teachers' performance level in teaching Reading in Senior High. This data was used in conducting the significant difference analysis.

Mann-Whitney U test. This non-parametric statistical tool was used to identify the significant difference between two independent and unequal groups in terms of their distributions. In this case those independent groups are the teachers and the students as they were compared to the perceived rating of teacher performance level in Teaching Reading skills in the senior high.

RESULTS

A. Teacher's Level of Performance in Teaching Reading Skills As Perceived by the Teachers

Table 3 below presents the teacher's level of performance in teaching reading skills as perceived by the teachers. The data indicates an overall weighted mean of 4.29, which indicates a high level of Performance. This suggests that the teachers view their teaching performance positively in terms of enhancing students' reading skills.

Table 3

Teacher's Level of Performance in teaching reading skills as perceived by the teachers (n=14)

	Statements	MEAN	SD	Description
1.	Teachers aim to enhance students' comprehension skills by instructing them on how to summarize texts and identify the main idea.	4.64	0.50	Very High
2.	Teachers provide instruction on creating graphic organizers, outlining techniques, and note-taking strategies to facilitate better understanding of texts and lessons.	4.64	0.50	Very High
3.	Teachers offer guidance through the use of guide questions or by encouraging students to ask questions about the lesson or reading materials, promoting deeper processing of their meaning.	4.5	0.65	Very High
4.	Teachers introduce difficult words in texts prior to reading, ensuring students are familiar with them to facilitate comprehension.	4.36	0.74	High
5.	Teachers consistently remind students to use dictionaries to expand their vocabulary and learn new words.	4.29	0.83	High
6.	Teachers use creative and engaging activities to help students learn new words effectively.	4.5	0.65	Very High
7.	Teachers actively correct students when they mispronounce words, assisting them in improving their pronunciation skills.	4.43	0.51	High
8.	Teachers in subjects unrelated to English also contribute to the improvement of students' reading skills.	4.36	0.63	High
9.	Teachers in other subjects help students with reading difficulties by providing assistive activities.	4.36	0.63	High

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10.	Teachers implement interactive reading development strategies like Peer Tutoring and Guided Collaborative Reading.	4	0.96	High
11.	Teachers use many activities for a single lesson to encourage collaboration and help develop their reading skills.	4.5	0.52	Very High
12.	Teachers cater to the different interests of students by offering a variety of activities to enhance their reading skills.	4.43	0.51	High
13.	Teachers consider the current skills of the students in giving reading materials and reading activities.	4.36	0.50	High
14.	Teachers vary strategies depending on students' strand and grade level.	4.5	0.52	Very High
15.	Teachers utilize books, technology, and engaging materials to create a stimulating learning environment for improving reading skills.	4.36	0.50	High
16.	The school/curriculum has lessons in both English and non-English subjects that are beneficial in the development of their reading skills.	4.36	0.74	High
17.	The school implements a program where struggling senior high readers are identified and are given assistance to improve their reading skills.	3.57	1.02	High
18.	The school fosters a reading culture that encourages students to read by designating reading time, providing ample reading materials, creating reading corners, and others.	3.71	1.14	High
19.	Teachers often take the initiative to call upon struggling senior high readers during free time to give additional support in improving their reading skills.	3.86	1.03	High
20.	Teachers prepare reading materials or reading kits specifically designed for senior high students who struggle with reading.	4.14	0.95	High
OVERALL		4.29	0.41	High

Legend: Very High 4.50-5.00 High 3.50-4.49 Moderate 2.50-3.49 Low 1.50-2.49 Very Low 1.00-1.49

B. Teacher's Level of Performance in Teaching Reading Skills As Perceived by the Students

Table 4 below presents the results in the Teacher's Level of Performance in teaching reading skills as perceived by the students. Analyzing the results based on the mean and standard deviation, it can be observed that the overall perception of the teaching performance of reading teachers as perceived by the students fell on High with an overall mean of 3.87.

Table 4

Teacher's Level of Performance in teaching reading skills as perceived by the students (n=205)

	Statements	MEAN	SD	Description
1.	Teachers aim to enhance students' comprehension skills by instructing them on how to summarize texts and identify the main idea.	4.27	0.84	High
2.	Teachers provide instruction on creating graphic organizers, outlining techniques, and note-taking strategies to facilitate better understanding of texts and lessons.	4.26	0.84	High
3.	Teachers offer guidance through the use of guide questions or by encouraging students to ask questions about the lesson or	4.17	0.99	High

	reading materials, promoting deeper processing of their meaning.			
4.	Teachers introduce difficult words in texts prior to reading, ensuring students are familiar with them to facilitate comprehension.	3.93	0.94	High
5.	Teachers consistently remind students to use dictionaries to expand their vocabulary and learn new words.	3.76	1.01	High
6.	Teachers use creative and engaging activities to help students learn new words effectively.	3.82	0.99	High
7.	Teachers actively correct students when they mispronounce words, assisting them in improving their pronunciation skills.	4.27	0.94	High
8.	Teachers in subjects unrelated to English also contribute to the improvement of students' reading skills.	4.2	0.88	High
9.	Teachers in other subjects help students with reading difficulties by providing assistive activities.	3.71	1.02	High
10.	Teachers implement interactive reading development strategies like Peer Tutoring and Guided Collaborative Reading.	3.56	1.1	High
11.	Teachers use many activities for a single lesson to encourage collaboration and help develop their reading skills.	3.79	0.97	High
12.	Teachers cater to the different interests of students by offering a variety of activities to enhance their reading skills.	3.8	0.92	High
13.	Teachers consider the current skills of the students in giving reading materials and reading activities.	3.52	0.96	High
14.	Teachers vary strategies depending on students' strand and grade level.	3.89	0.98	High
15.	Teachers utilize books, technology, and engaging materials to create a stimulating learning environment for improving reading skills.	4.2	0.91	High
16.	The school/curriculum has lessons in both English and non-English subjects that are beneficial in the development of their reading skills.	4.16	1	High
17.	The school implements a program where struggling senior high readers are identified and are given assistance to improve their reading skills.	3.55	1.23	High
18.	The school fosters a reading culture that encourages students to read by designating reading time, providing ample reading materials, creating reading corners, and others.	3.64	1.07	High
19.	Teachers often take the initiative to call upon struggling senior high readers during free time to give additional support in improving their reading skills.	3.36	1.19	High
20.	Teachers prepare reading materials or reading kits specifically designed for senior high students who struggle with reading.	3.48	1.24	High
	OVERALL	3.87	0.65	High

Legend: Very High 4.50-5.00 High 3.50-4.49 Moderate 2.50-3.49 Low 1.50-2.49 Very Low 1.00-1.49

C. Significant Difference Between the Teacher's and Student's Perception

This study further investigated whether there is a significant difference in the perception of teachers' performance level in teaching reading skills between students and teachers themselves. To do this, the Mann-Whitney U test was employed. Shown below are the result and discussion.

Table 5

The significant difference in the perception of teachers' performance level in teaching reading skills

Groups	N	Mean	SD	Mann U	p	Remarks
Students	205	3.867	.651	860.50	.012	Significant
Teachers	14	4.293	.413			

As shown in the table above, results indicate that students' mean perception score of teachers' performance in teaching reading skills was 3.867 ($SD=.651$). On the other hand, teachers' self-perception score of their performance was 4.293 ($SD=.413$).

The Mann-Whitney U test revealed a significant difference in the perception of teachers' performance levels between students and teachers ($U = 860.50, p = .012$). This implies that there is a notable distinction in how students perceive teachers' effectiveness in teaching reading compared to teachers' self-assessments.

DISCUSSION

While the majority of indicators reflect positive perceptions, some areas for improvement are identified. The indicators related to the identification and support of struggling students ($M=3.57, SD=1.02$) received relatively lower mean scores, suggesting the need for further attention and enhancement of intervention programs. Additionally, the school can focus on developing a more robust reading culture ($M=3.86, SD=1.03$) to further promote students' reading engagement. The findings are consistent with previous research suggesting that effective reading comprehension instruction involves teaching students to use metacognitive strategies, such as monitoring comprehension, generating and asking questions, summarizing texts, and using graphic organizers (Reading Rockets, n.d.; Texas Education Agency, n.d.). The findings also support the idea that vocabulary and pronunciation are essential components of reading comprehension (ThoughtCo, 2019). However, the findings also reveal some areas for improvement, such as identifying and supporting struggling students and developing a stronger reading culture in the school. These areas may require more attention and resources from the school administration and teachers.

Interestingly, the students' data aligns with the data provided by the teachers, indicating that indicators associated with identifying and supporting struggling students have relatively lower mean scores ($M=3.71, SD=1.02$), further underscoring the necessity for additional attention and enhancement of intervention programs, as well as a stronger establishment of a reading culture within the school ($M=3.87, SD=0.65$). It is important to strengthen intervention programs and foster a more robust reading culture within the

school to address these areas of concern. This underscores the significance of continuous professional development for teachers and the creation of a supportive environment conducive to fostering reading engagement and assisting students with reading difficulties. According to TeacherPH (n.d.), reading intervention strategies are interventions implemented to aid students struggling with reading in various ways. These strategies may encompass reading aloud, phonics, word analysis, guided reading, partner reading, reading clinics, individualized reading instruction, literacy centers, and tutoring. The Department of Education (DepEd) also advocates for the use of the Reading Progress Tool by teachers, parents, and other reading specialists to assess learners' reading skills (DepEd, 2021). This tool serves as a self-instructional application designed to assist teachers in enhancing their learners' reading proficiency and cultivating a passion for reading.

The significant difference in perception has several implications. Firstly, it suggests a disparity between students' assessment and teachers' self-perception of their teaching performance in reading skills. This incongruity may arise from differences in expectations, perspectives, or communication barriers between students and teachers (Hattie & Timperley, 2007; Klassen & Tze, 2014). It further implies that students might have a more critical or less favorable view of the teaching methods employed in the classroom. This divergence may indicate a need for teachers to gain a better understanding of students' perspectives and tailor their instructional strategies to meet student's needs and expectations (Guskey & Bailey, 2019; Tomlinson & Imbeau, 2010).

Conclusions

In conclusion, this study contributes valuable insights into the perceptions of both students and teachers regarding the teacher's performance in teaching reading skills in senior high schools. While the majority of indicators reflect positive perceptions, certain areas for improvement have been identified, particularly concerning the identification and support of struggling students and the development of a stronger reading culture within schools. Notably, students and teachers share aligned perceptions regarding these areas, emphasizing the need for enhanced intervention programs and a supportive learning environment conducive to reading engagement. The rejection of the Null Hypothesis, as evidenced by the significant difference in perception between students and teachers, underscores the necessity for educators to better understand students' perspectives and tailor instructional strategies accordingly.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, it is recommended that senior high schools invest in Continuous Professional Development (CPD) for teachers to enhance instructional strategies for teaching reading skills, bolster intervention programs tailored to support struggling readers, cultivate a reading-positive environment through initiatives like book clubs and literacy events, facilitate open communication and collaboration among

stakeholders to address differing perceptions of teaching effectiveness, and employ data-driven decision-making processes to inform targeted interventions and enhancements in reading instruction. Furthermore, future researchers could enhance the current study by increasing the number of teacher respondents to strengthen the reliability of the results to more accurately represent the general population.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Throughout the study, the researcher upheld various ethical standards. These includes ensuring the credibility of the research through the use of valid evidence, subjecting the study to the evaluation and approval of the institution's Ethics Review Committee, and honoring intellectual property rights. Before conducting interviews, participants were given enough time to review and consent to the informed consent form, which presented unbiased study details, informed them of their right to withdraw, assured confidentiality of data, and guaranteed anonymity. In order to safeguard the welfare of respondents, the researcher refrained from discrimination and took measures to minimize any potential adverse effects. Additionally, the researchers ensured there were no conflicts of interest and that the data was utilized solely for research purposes.

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